

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL – 1

INFORMATION SHEET AND SELF-STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE

Please Note: The information sheet was designed as the part of the dissertation project with a different title.

Title: HEALTHY EATING INTERVENTION FOR ANALYSING NUTRITIONAL KNOWLEDGE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL CHILDREN

I, Ritika Kapoor, student at Centre for Public Health, Panjab University, Chandigarh, is conducting a study on "**HEALTHY EATING INTERVENTION FOR ANALYSING NUTRITIONAL KNOWLEDGE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL CHILDREN**". Two questionnaires will be provided to you, which of Knowledge, only take 15-20 minutes of your time, for each questionnaire. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of your Knowledge regarding Nutrition and your practices regarding Healthy Eating and with the help of the lecture given to test your improvement regarding nutrition. Your participation in this study is voluntary and you can withdraw from study at any time without explaining reasons. Your responses will be used only for research purposes and you are completely anonymous. Confidentiality will also be strictly maintained. Thank you for cooperation and support.

- I have understood information provided on this form and about the research study.

Signature

Date

Contact persons: For further Information / questions, you can contact us at the following address:

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PRE-INTERVENTION QUESTIONNAIRE

PERFORMA NO. -

DATE-

Please read all the questions/statements carefully and answer/respond to all the questions honestly as per instructions given in questions/statements. Your responses will be only used for research purposes. You will be completely anonymous. CONFIDENTIALITY will also be maintained. Thank you for your cooperation and support.

SECTION-1

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

(Please Circle or Tick next to appropriate response as per options given below)

1. Age (Years) - _____

2. Gender :

- a. Male
- b. Female
- c. Other

3. Residential Area –

- a. Urban
- b. Rural

4. Religion -

- a. Hindu
- b. Muslim
- c. Sikh

- d. Christian
 - e. Other
5. Studying in Standard -
- a. 5th
 - b. 6th
 - c. 7th
 - d. 8th
6. Earning Member of family –
- a. Father
 - b. Mother
 - c. Both a and b
7. Occupation of Father/Mother - _____

SECTION-2

KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NUTRITION

(Please Circle or Tick next to appropriate response as per options given below)

1. On a scale of 1 to 5, rate yourself in terms of good health, while 1 being poor and 5 being excellent.
- a. 1 = poor
 - b. 2 = fair
 - c. 3 = good
 - d. 4 = very good
 - e. 5 = excellent
2. What does the definition of Nutrition, as given in the NCERT book?
- a. Science of foods

- b. Science of nutrients and their actions within the human body including ingestion.
 - c. Both a and b
 - d. Neither a nor b
 - e. Do not know
3. What are the components of balanced diet? (May tick multiple following components)
- a. Carbohydrates
 - b. Fats
 - c. Proteins
 - d. Vitamins
 - e. Minerals
 - f. Water
 - g. All of the above
 - h. Do not know
4. Besides carbohydrates, a major source of energy in our food is constituted by:
- a. Proteins
 - b. Fats
 - c. Minerals
 - d. Vitamins
5. Which of the following nutrients is needed for a healthy immune system?
- a. Calcium
 - b. Iodine
 - c. Vitamin K
 - d. Vitamin C
6. Which of the following food constituents is not digested but is still important to us?
- a. Vitamins
 - b. Minerals
 - c. Proteins
 - d. Fibre

SECTION-3

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES FOR HEALTHY EATING HABITS

(Please Circle or Tick next to appropriate response as per options given below. Answer the below questions on the basis of your daily routine for the previous week)

1. Do you like eating healthy food?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Do not know

2. How many meals do you eat in a day?
 - a. 1 meal a day
 - b. 2 meals a day
 - c. 3 meals a day
 - d. 4 meals a day
 - e. 5 meals a day
 - f. 6 meals a day

3. How often you consume breakfast?
 - a. Once a week
 - b. Twice a week
 - c. Thrice a week
 - d. Four times a week
 - e. Five times a week
 - f. Six times week
 - g. Yes, Everyday
 - h. No, Never
 - i. Cannot say

4. What type of dinner meal do you consume on a regular basis?
 - a. Light (Less amount of fat content in food)
 - b. Heavy (High amount of fat content in food)
 - c. Cannot say

5. How many Glasses of water do you consume in a day?
 - a. 2 glasses a day
 - b. 4 glasses a day
 - c. 6 glasses a day
 - d. 8 glasses a day
 - e. More than 8 glasses a day

6. How often do you eat sprouted pulses and green leafy vegetables?
 - a. Every time in main diet
 - b. At least once a day
 - c. 3 to 4 times a week
 - d. Once a week
 - e. Less than once a week
 - f. Do not consume

7. How often do you consume eggs?
 - a. At least once a day
 - b. 3 to 4 times a week
 - c. Once a week
 - d. Less than once a week
 - e. Do not consume

8. How often do you consume non-vegetarian food items like chicken, fish, etc.?
 - a. At least once a day
 - b. 3 to 4 times a week
 - c. Once a week
 - d. Less than once a week
 - e. Do not consume

9. How frequently do you eat fruits?

- a. Every time in main diet
- b. At least once a day
- c. Twice a day
- d. 3 to 4 times a week
- e. Once a week
- f. Less than a week

10. How frequently do you consume salad?

- a. Every time in main diet
- b. At least once a day
- c. Twice a day
- d. 3 to 4 times a week
- e. Once a week
- f. Less than a week

11. How many times do you in a week consume milk?

- a. Once everyday
- b. Twice a day
- c. 5 to 6 times a week
- d. 3 to 4 times a week
- e. Once or twice a week
- f. Less than a week
- g. Do not consume

12. How frequently do you consume fast food/street food?

- a. At least once a day
- b. Twice a day
- c. 3 to 4 times a week
- d. Once a week
- e. Less than a week
- f. Do not consume

13. How often do you have sweets?

- a. At least once a day
- b. Twice a day
- c. 3 to 4 times a week
- d. Once a week
- e. Less than a week
- f. Do not consume

14. Do you wash your hands before and after eating your meal?

- Yes, Always
- No, never
- Sometimes

POST INTERVENTION QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION-2

KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NUTRITION

(Please Circle or Tick next to appropriate response as per options given below)

1. On a scale of 1 to 5, how will you now rate yourself for good health, with 1 being poor and 5 being excellent?
 - a. 1 = poor
 - b. 2 = fair
 - c. 3 = good
 - d. 4 = very good
 - e. 5 = excellent

2. What will you do to stay healthy?
 - a. Healthy diet
 - b. Physical exercise
 - c. Proper sleep
 - d. Maintaining proper hygiene
 - e. All of the above

3. What are components of balanced diet?
 - a. Carbohydrates
 - b. Fats
 - c. Proteins
 - d. Vitamins
 - e. Minerals
 - f. Water
 - g. All of the above
 - h. None of the above

4. Besides carbohydrates, a major source of energy in our food is constituted by:
 - a. Proteins
 - b. Fats
 - c. Minerals
 - d. Vitamins

5. Which of the following nutrients is needed for a healthy immune system?
 - a. Calcium
 - b. Iodine
 - c. Vitamin K
 - d. Vitamin C

6. Which of the following food constituents is not digested but is still important to us?
 - e. Vitamins
 - f. Minerals
 - g. Proteins
 - h. Fibre

SECTION-3

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES FOR HEALTHY EATING HABITS

(Please Circle or Tick next to appropriate response as per options given below)

1. Will you now follow healthy eating habits for your good health?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Do not know

2. How many times should you now eat in a day?
 - a. 1 meal a day
 - b. 2 meals a day
 - c. 3 meals a day
 - d. 4 meals a day
 - e. 5 meals a day
 - f. 6 meals a day

3. How often will you now consume breakfast on weekly basis?
 - a. Yes, always
 - b. 5 to 6 times a week
 - c. 3 to 4 times a week
 - d. 1 to 2 times a week
 - e. No, never

4. Now what kind of dinner will you prefer?
 - a. Light
 - b. Heavy
 - c. Cannot say

5. How many glasses of water will you now consume in a day?
 - a. 2 glasses a day
 - b. 4 glasses a day
 - c. 6 glasses a day
 - d. 8 glasses a day
 - e. More than 8 glasses a day

6. How often will you now consume sprouted pulses and green leafy vegetables in your meals?
 - a. Every time in main diet
 - b. At least once a day
 - c. 3 to 4 times a week
 - d. Once a week
 - e. Less than once a week

7. How often will you now consume eggs?
 - a. At least once a day
 - b. 3 to 4 times a week
 - c. Once a week
 - d. Less than once a week
 - e. Will not consume

8. How many times a week should you consume non-vegetarian food items like fish, chicken etc.?
 - a. Once a week
 - b. Twice a week
 - c. Thrice a week
 - d. All of the above
 - e. None of the above

9. Now, how many times will you have fruits on a weekly basis?
 - g. Every time in main diet
 - h. At least once a day
 - i. Twice a day
 - j. 3 to 4 times a week
 - k. Once a week
 - l. Less than a week

10. How often will you now consume salad in diets?

- g. Every time in main diet
- h. At least once a day
- i. Twice a day
- j. 3 to 4 times a week
- k. Once a week
- l. Less than a week

11. How many times will you know consume milk, in a week?

- a. Once everyday
- b. Twice a day
- c. 5 to 6 times a week
- d. 3 to 4 times a week
- e. Once or twice a week
- f. Less than a week

12. How frequently will now you consume fast food/street food?

- a. At least once a day
- b. Twice a day
- c. 3 to 4 times a week
- d. Once a week
- e. Less than a week
- f. Will not consume

13. Will you now have sweets on a regular basis?

- a. Yes
- b. No

14. Will you now wash your hands before and after eating your meal?

- a. Yes, Always
- b. No, Never

